

SYNTHESIS OF 0.95MgTiO₃-0.05CaTiO₃ CERAMICS BY REACTION-SINTERING

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Abstract

0.95MgTiO₃-0.05CaTiO₃ (MCT) ceramics prepared using a reaction-sintering process were investigated. Without any calcination involved, the mixture of Mg(OH)₂, CaCO₃ and TiO₂ was pressed and sintered directly. MCT ceramics were obtained after 2-6 h sintering at 1150-1250°C. Secondary phase MgTi₂O₅ as in MgTiO₃ prepared by the conventional mixed oxide route was not detected. The maximum density 3.62g/cm³ (93.8% of the theoretical value) was obtained at 1230°C/2 h. For 2 h sintering, grains of size less than 10 μm were formed. Abnormal grains (>70μm) were observed in pellets sintered for 4 and 6 h due to the secondary grain growth.

1 Introduction

Dielectric resonators used in microwave frequency have been widely investigated due to the fast growth of satellite and mobile communication systems. MgTiO₃ (MT) was reported to exhibit good dielectric properties of ε_r ~17, Q×f ~160,000 at 7 GHz and τ_f ~ -50 ppm/°C. As CaTiO₃ (CT) with dielectric properties of ε_r ~170, Q×f ~ 3,600 at 7 GHz and τ_f ~ 800 ppm/°C was mixed into MT, τ_f near 0 ppm/°C could be obtained [1-4].

Synthesis of MT-based ceramics has been reported in many studies by solid-state reaction methods [5-7], sol-gel [8], coprecipitation[9], thermal decomposition of peroxide precursors [10] and mechanochemical routes [11-12]. High temperature around 1400°C is required in conventional solid-state synthesis from oxide precursors. Phase pure MgTiO₃ is difficult to obtain by solid-state reactions because of the formation of some metastable titanate phases. MgTi₂O₅ was still found in MgTiO₃ ceramic even by the

mechanochemical process [11]. Dielectric properties of MgTi₂O₅ are ε_r ~17.4, Q×f ~47,000 GHz and τ_f ~ -66 ppm/°C [13].

Reaction-sintering process is a simple and effective route to obtain ceramics with high density. The mixture of the raw materials is sintered directly with the calcination step bypassed. Liou and co-workers proposed Pb(Mg_{1/3}Nb_{2/3})O₃ (PMN), Pb(Mg_{1/3}Nb_{2/3})O₃-PbTiO₃ (PMN-PT) and Pb(Fe_{0.5}Nb_{0.5})O₃ (PFN) ceramics produced via a reaction-sintering process [14-16]. PMN ceramics with 99.5% of the theoretical density and high dielectric constant 19,900 (1 kHz) were obtained. This reaction-sintering process had also been successfully used to produce other complex perovskite relaxor ceramics [17-21]. Recently, Liou et al. produced some ceramics used for microwave dielectric components such as BaTi₄O₉, Ba₅Nb₄O₁₅, Sr₅Nb₄O₁₅, CaNb₂O₆ and ZnNb₂O₆ via this direct sintering method [22-25]. In this study, we try to obtain 0.95MgTiO₃-0.05CaTiO₃ ceramics by the reaction-sintering process.

2 Experimental procedure

All samples were prepared from reagent-grade powders: Mg(OH)₂ (95%), TiO₂ (99.9%), and CaCO₃ (99.9%). Appropriate amounts of raw materials for 0.95MgTiO₃-0.05CaTiO₃ (MCT) were weighed. The mixture was milled in acetone with zirconia balls for 12 h and then dried, pulverized and pressed into pellets of 12 mm in diameter and 1-2 mm thick. The pellets were heated at a rate 10°C/min and sintered in a covered alumina crucible at temperatures ranging from 1150°C to 1300°C for 2-6 h in air.

Crystalline phases of the sintered pellets were identified with X-ray diffraction (XRD). Microstructures were analyzed by scanning electron microscopy (SEM). The density of sintered pellets was measured by the Archimedes method.

3 Results and discussion

Fig. 1 shows the XRD profiles of MCT ceramics using $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$ and with 1-3 mol% excess $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$ after sintered at $1250^\circ\text{C}/2$ h. The main phase MgTiO_3 formed and the minor phase CaTiO_3 was also found in the profiles. MgTi_2O_5 often formed in MgTiO_3 as a stable intermediate phase by mixed oxide route [2]. MgTi_2O_5 phase formed in MCT ceramics using MgO (Fig. 1 (a)) by the reaction-sintering process was not observed. This proves the MgTiO_3 -based ceramics could be obtained by the reaction-sintering process. This simple process is effective not only in preparing BaTi_4O_9 , $\text{Ba}_5\text{Nb}_4\text{O}_{15}$, $\text{Sr}_5\text{Nb}_4\text{O}_{15}$, CaNb_2O_6 , ZnNb_2O_6 and Pb-based complex perovskite ceramics but also effective in preparing ceramics with MT and CT mixed phase.

Fig. 1. XRD profiles of MCT ceramics using (a) MgO , (b) $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$ and with (c) 1, (d) 2 (e) 3 mol% excess $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$ and sintered at $1250^\circ\text{C}/2$ h. (MgTiO_3 : ICDD # 00-006-0494, CaTiO_3 : JCPDS # 89-8033, ●: MgTi_2O_5)

In Fig. 2, the density value of MCT increased with sintering temperature and saturated above 1230°C . The maximum density $3.62\text{g}/\text{cm}^3$ (93.8% of the theoretical value) was obtained at $1230^\circ\text{C}/2$ h. Huang *et al.* reported MCT ceramics of density 3.49 - $3.72\text{g}/\text{cm}^3$ with addition of sintering aids Bi_2O_3 , CuO and B_2O_3 . They used conventional mixed oxide route and pellets were calcined at $1100^\circ\text{C}/3$ - 4 h then sintered at 1200 - $1300^\circ\text{C}/3$ - 4 h [2-4]. Maximum density $3.85\text{g}/\text{cm}^3$ could be obtained in MCT using MgO via the reaction-sintering process and sintered at $1250^\circ\text{C}/4$ h. Lower density in MCT using $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$ may caused by the fast grain growth and resulted in lots of isolated pores inside the pellets.

Fig. 2. Density of MCT ceramics with 2 mol% excess $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$ sintered at various temperatures and times.

Fig. 3. SEM photos of MCT ceramics with 2 mol% excess $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$ sintered at 1150°C for (a) 2 h, (b) 4 h and (c) 6 h.

The SEM photos of MCT ceramics sintered at 1150°C for 2 h are shown in Fig. 3. For 2 h sintering, grains of size less than $10\ \mu\text{m}$ were formed. Abnormal grains ($>70\ \mu\text{m}$) were observed in pellets sintered for 4 and 6 h due to the secondary grain growth. It can be noted that grains with two different sizes formed in MCT pellets. The larger grains are MgTiO_3 and the smaller grains are CaTiO_3 or MgTiO_3 . In the study of Huang and Weng, large grains in MCT ceramics with B_2O_3 addition were recognized as MgTiO_3 and small grains might be

CaTiO₃ or MgTiO₃ [2]. In doped MgTiO₃-CaTiO₃ prepared via conventional solid-state reaction method, Woo et al. found that large grains were identified as MgTiO₃, containing dispersed small CaTiO₃ crystallites inside. CaTiO₃ and MgTiO₃ phases were separated due to virtually no solid solubility between them because of different crystal structures [26]. Wing et al. also observed similar morphology in calcium magnesium titanate system. Large-scale inhomogeneities occurred on the scale of 100–200 μm and showed very little calcium content [27].

4 Conclusions

0.95MgTiO₃-0.05CaTiO₃ ceramics have been obtained successfully by a reaction-sintering process using Mg(OH)₂. Secondary phase MgTi₂O₅ as in MgTiO₃ prepared by the conventional mixed oxide route was not detected. The maximum density 3.62g/cm³ (93.8% of the theoretical value) was obtained at 1230°C/2 h. For 2 h sintering, grains of size less than 10 μm were formed. Abnormal grains (>70μm) were observed in pellets sintered for 4 and 6 h due to the secondary grain growth.

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